

CCG POLICY BRIEF

Economic Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling: Solar Photovoltaic (PV)

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Summary

Solar photovoltaic (PV) power generation is an important technology in the global transition towards a net zero energy system, as it can provide low-cost, scalable clean power generation. Many countries across the globe are developing robust policy frameworks to support the rapid scale-up of utility-scale and distributed solar PV and have placed a heavy emphasis on its deployment in their energy and climate strategies.

The formulation of these strategies relies on technical insights gained from energy system models (ESMs), such as OSeMOSYS. However, the decarbonisation pathways generated by ESMs are very sensitive to input assumptions over the relative costs of generation technologies, including solar PV. Costs of deploying solar PV vary substantially between different countries – potentially by up to 3x – with limited empirical data available in the open literature for many countries (particularly in the Global South). Here, we present data on the global costs of solar PV power and discuss how these global ranges taken from the open literature could be used to help support the development of more accurate technical insights for climate

Key Policy Recommendations

- Solar PV will play an important role in the decarbonisation of national electricity systems and accurate technical insights from ESMs and other tools should be used to guide deployment strategies.
- The sensitivity of ESMs to the costs of solar PV needs to be accounted for when technical insights are used to guide the development of policy frameworks and/or Nationally Determined Contributions.
- Researchers and other stakeholders operating in countries with data availability issues should clearly present assumptions used for ESMs, especially when supporting policy development.
- Global cost ranges can be a useful tool to situate cost assumptions for ESMs but are not a substitute for direct stakeholder engagement

Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling of Solar PV

Introduction

Solar photovoltaic (PV) power has a critical role to play in the decarbonisation of the global sector by providing a cheap, scalable source of low-carbon electricity across the globe. The International Energy Agency predicts in its Stated Policies Scenario that the installed capacity globally could more than double to 500 GW in 2030 from an existing 220 GW in 2022 [1]. With advancements in technology and rapidly decreasing costs, solar PV has emerged as one of the most accessible and scalable renewable energy solutions, and alongside onshore wind and electric vehicles it is expected to be one of the key technologies for the energy transition.

Despite its rapid deployment and increased maturity over the last two decades, there is still substantial uncertainty over the future costs of utility-scale solar PV, especially in countries without any empirical data and/or prior deployment of utility-scale solar PV. The total installed costs for utility-scale solar PV reported by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) for 2022 varied from a low of USD 640/kW in India to a high of USD 1,905/kW in Japan [2], a ratio of nearly 3x, highlighting the care needed when drawing cost assumptions from empirical data for the deployment of solar PV in other countries.

Whilst research has examined the impact of including country or region specific costs for solar PV [3], there are no studies which collated the technoeconomic parameters from the open literature base that are key to accurately calculating the costs of solar PV. This policy brief outlines a curated dataset that presents global ranges of the technoeconomic parameters (eg total installed cost, operating costs, operational lifetimes) which are key to modelling the cost of solar PV, drawn from the open and grey literature. The aim of this brief is to discuss the challenges around data availability for solar PV, especially in the Global South, whilst providing energy system modellers and other stakeholders with a method of situating and justifying their cost assumptions in the absence of empirical data.

Drawing upon the existing literature base

Technoeconomic data on solar PV were gathered to inform the assumptions used in large-scale energy systems modelling tools such as the OSeMOSYS [4]. Relevant data were collected from websites, reports, academic articles, and databases of national and international organisations. The data covers the range of parameters needed for the technoeconomic analysis of utility-scale solar photovoltaic deployment including operating costs, capital costs, construction times and total operational lifetime. The dataset has been made openly accessible in the Zenodo Data Repository and can be accessed via the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/10886016>. The dataset shared on the Zenodo link contains the sources that were used to populate the database.

Global current capital costs for solar PV

Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of overnight capital costs for the deployment of solar PV, taken across 2020–2024. The costs extracted from the open literature between 2020–2024 show substantial variation, with a median value of 1,041, 1,354, and 940 USD/kW for fixed axis solar PV and solar PV equipped with single or double axis tracking. Solar PV values stated in the literature without information on whether these costs were for fixed or tracking systems were categorised as “Unspecified”. . Data that were found in the open literature were predominantly from countries in Europe, North America, Asia, Oceania, and the Middle East, with substantial data gaps for the rest of the world.

Figure 1: Range of a) capital costs and b) fixed operating costs in 2020–2024 for solar farms, by category and stated in 2023 US dollar terms. The lower and upper bounds of each shaded box represent the lower and upper quartile of the data (25th and 75th percentile respectively), with the central line representing the median. Whiskers represent the range of values falling within 1.5 times the inter-quartile range, and outliers are shown with diamonds. The 25th, 50th, and 75th percentile values are written to the left of each bar.

Using global ranges to address empirical data gaps

Solar PV will play an important role globally in supporting the transition to a clean energy system, especially in countries and regions where there has been limited deployment of solar PV historically (which includes much of the Global South). The International Energy Agency estimates in its Net Zero Emissions by 2050 scenario that more than 70 GW of additional solar PV will be deployed each year up to 2030 across Africa, Latin America, the Caribbean, Middle East, and Southeast Asia, displacing both natural-gas and coal-fired power generation [1].

Understanding the current and future costs of deployment will be key to the effective design of policy support and the development of appropriate integrated energy and climate strategies. Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of capital costs between 2020–2024 by region (where available) and projected global costs in 2030 and 2050, whilst **Figure 3** shows the range of financing costs reporting by world region. Given the capital intensive nature of solar power, the cost of electricity is highly dependent on both the financing costs and upfront capital costs, which as demonstrated in both Figures can vary substantially. **Error! Reference source not found.** Data gaps therefore create significant difficulties for energy system modellers around the selection and justification of cost assumptions for solar PV, as incorrect assumptions can lead to substantially different conclusions on the cost of electricity.

Figure 2: Range of capital costs for solar PV farms in a) 2020–2024 for each world region, where available, and b) global projections for 2030 and 2050. Costs are stated in 2023 US dollar terms.

Figure 3: Range of financing costs for solar farms in each world region, where available, in 2020–2024.

In countries and regions with limited deployment of solar PV, it is important for energy system modellers to clearly highlight the cost assumptions used in power and energy system modelling, as the decarbonisation pathways and technical insights developed from modelling may be highly sensitive to the costs of solar PV. Transparent documentation of assumptions and methodologies will also increase confidence in the modelling results, facilitating informed decision-making by policymakers and other stakeholders. The ranges presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** are intended to serve as a useful tool to situate assumptions in energy system models (ESMs) for these countries against empirical data taken from other countries and regions,

addressing the data gaps whilst still providing robust technical insights to support the development of energy and climate strategies by policymakers.

Prioritising transparency and data sharing amongst stakeholders will also be essential to enhance the accuracy and utility of ESMs. By openly sharing data and methodologies, academic researchers, government ministries, industry professionals, and other stakeholders can work collaboratively to address data gaps, compare and contrast their assumptions, and so improve the reliability of energy system modelling outcomes. Given the potential sensitivity of ESMs to the costs of solar PV, energy system modellers should also conduct sensitivity tests to assess the robustness of their models. Understanding how variations in cost assumptions impact model outcomes will be crucial for making informed decisions and developing resilient energy transition pathways, and situating their assumptions against the global cost curve could be a useful way of exploring model sensitivities.

However, whilst the global ranges from the open literature presented in this work can provide valuable insights and offer a way to address empirical data gaps, they should complement, not replace, direct engagement with private sector stakeholders. Collaborating with industry partners can enrich data collection efforts and ensure that ESMs accurately reflect real-world conditions and the true costs of solar PV.

Conclusions

Addressing the challenges of data availability for solar PV will be critical to accelerating the energy transition, particularly in countries in the Global South where there is limited experience with the deployment of solar PV. By recognising the sensitivity of ESMs to assumptions over the costs of solar PV, prioritising transparency and data sharing, and justifying cost assumptions in regions with limited empirical data, stakeholders can enhance the accuracy and reliability of the scenarios generated from ESMs. This will help ensure their accuracy, utility, and relevance to policy. Whilst global ranges from the open literature can serve as useful reference points, engaging with private sector stakeholders will be essential for understanding and capturing the complexities of real-world deployment scenarios.

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Author Statement

The work described in this policy brief was funded by the South Africa-driven Modelling Capacity and Communication (ADMeCC) project, with co-funding from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG brings together leading research organisations and is led out of the STEER Centre, Loughborough University.

Both of these programmes are funded by the UK Government's Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO).

However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK Government's official policies.

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Citation

Hatton, L., Staffell, I., Johnson, N., Dixon, L., Mosongo, B., De Kock, S., Marquard, A., Howells, M. *Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling: Solar Power*. Climate Compatible Growth Data for Energy System Modelling Series (Version 1).